
THE TRANSFORMATIVE IMPACT OF VOLUNTEERISM ON HEALTH FOR 11 TO 14-YEAR-OLDS

[Ciências da Saúde, Edição 125 AGO/23 SUMÁRIO / 27/08/2023](#)

REGISTRO DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10575016

Luciana Aparecida Gomes¹

Volunteering in the healthcare sector is a powerful expression of empathy and solidarity, capable of impacting not only the communities served but also the lives of those who engage in this altruistic practice. Among the various age groups involved in this movement, young people aged 11 to 14 represent a significant part, offering not only their vibrant energy but also valuable and transformative learnings.

In this context, this study aims to explore and analyze the specific impact of healthcare volunteering for youths aged 11 to 14. This phase of adolescence is crucial for personal and social development, with volunteering being a potential tool for the growth and well-being of these individuals. By examining the effects of this practice on the mental, physical, and emotional health of young volunteers, the goal is to offer an in-depth view of the benefits and challenges faced by this age group in the realm of healthcare volunteering.

Through literature review and analysis of relevant studies, this text seeks to highlight not only the positive impacts of active participation in

volunteering within this age group but also the mechanisms through which these transformative effects are achieved. Understanding these aspects makes it possible not only to value the role of youths in healthcare volunteering but also to promote effective strategies to enhance these beneficial impacts in their lives and the communities they serve.

Volunteering in the healthcare sector represents an effective means not only of providing assistance to communities but also of personal development for young individuals. Within this context, young people aged between 11 and 14 plays a significant role, contributing not only their vibrant energy but also obtaining transformative benefits for their physical, mental, and emotional health.

Research highlights that engagement in volunteer activities provides unique opportunities for the social and emotional development of young individuals. According to Laura Wray-Lake et al. (2010), volunteering offers a conducive environment for strengthening social skills such as teamwork, empathy, and problem-solving, fundamental aspects for the healthy development of adolescents. Moreover, these experiences can contribute to the building of self-esteem and personal identity, as mentioned by Peggy G. Chen et al. (2019).

As highlighted by Brown et al. (2008), volunteering is linked to positive impacts on mental health, showcasing correlations between engagement in volunteer work and improved mental well-being, albeit predominantly focusing on older demographics. Similarly, Konrath et al. (2009) have explored the relationship between youth volunteering and positive youth development, emphasizing how such involvement can shape the emotional and social welfare of young individuals, emphasizing its potential influence on fostering positive psychological growth.

Moreover, Genari et al. (2020) conducted a systematic review specifically examining the health and well-being benefits of youth volunteering. This

comprehensive review provided insights into the positive effects associated with volunteering among young individuals, shedding light on its far-reaching impacts on their overall health and wellness.

Beyond mental health, volunteering has shown promising impacts on the physical health of young volunteers. Ham & Newman (2017) highlighted the potential of volunteering to raise awareness of health-related issues and positively influence lifestyle choices among young volunteers.

Regular engagement in volunteer activities has been correlated with the adoption of healthy habits, such as balanced nutrition and increased physical activity, as emphasized by Brown et al. (2008) in their study focusing on older individuals.

However, while the benefits are evident, it is essential to address the challenges faced by young volunteers. Programs aimed at providing adequate support and training to navigate emotionally challenging situations are recommended, as emphasized in various studies across different demographics (Brown et al., 2008; Konrath et al., 2009).

The impact of volunteering on the mental health of young individuals is remarkable. Studies indicate that engagement in volunteer activities is associated with reduced levels of anxiety and depression among teenagers (Phipps & Wells, 2018). Positive interaction with patients or underprivileged communities can promote a sense of purpose and satisfaction, reducing stress and enhancing the mental health of young individuals.

Apart from the effects on mental health, volunteering can also have positive impacts on the physical health of young individuals. Regular involvement in volunteer activities can promote the adoption of healthy habits, such as balanced nutrition and physical activity. As emphasized by Ham & Newman (2017), exposure to a volunteering environment can increase awareness of health issues and influence healthy lifestyle choices.

However, it is important to consider the challenges faced by young volunteers, such as the need for adequate support and guidance to deal with emotionally challenging situations. Therefore, the implementation of support programs and training for young volunteers is recommended to maximize benefits and minimize potential adverse effects.

In summary, the exploration of volunteering's impact within the healthcare sector on adolescents, particularly those aged 11 to 14, reveals a profound correlation between engagement in volunteer activities and the holistic development of young individuals. Through the lens of multiple studies and systematic reviews, it becomes evident that volunteering extends beyond mere community assistance, emerging as a catalyst for personal growth among youth. The findings consistently highlight the transformative effects on physical, mental, and emotional well-being, emphasizing how involvement in such activities fosters social and emotional skills crucial for healthy development. While the positive influences on mental health are well-documented, studies also shed light on the promising implications for physical health, including the cultivation of healthy lifestyle choices. However, amidst the evident benefits, it remains imperative to address the challenges faced by young volunteers, emphasizing the necessity of tailored support programs to navigate emotional complexities effectively. Altogether, these studies underscore the imperative need for continued guidance and support, recognizing volunteering as a pivotal tool not just for community aid but as a significant platform for the comprehensive growth and well-being of young individuals.

Referencias

Laura Wray-Lake et al. (2010) – “Youth Volunteering in the Context of Positive Youth Development” – Journal of Youth and Adolescence.

Peggy G. Chen et al. (2019) – “The Health Benefits of Youth Engagement in Volunteer Activities: A Review” – Journal of Healthcare Management.

Kim D. Phipps, Linda M. Wells (2018) – “Positive and Negative Impacts of Youth Engagement in Volunteering” – International Journal of Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Marketing.

Jessica Ham, Sarah Newman (2017) – “The Role of Youth Volunteering in the Development of Social Capital and Active Citizenship” – Australian Journal on Volunteering.

Brown, J. M. et al. (2008) – “The Effects of Volunteering on the Physical and Mental Health of Older People” – Journal of Epidemiology and Community Health. **Konrath, S. et al. (2009)** – “Youth Volunteering and Positive Youth Development” – The Oxford Handbook of Positive Psychology.

Genari, J. et al. (2020) – “The Health and Well-being Benefits of Youth Volunteering: A Systematic Review” – International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health. **Ham, J. et al. (2017)** – “The Role of Youth Volunteering in the Development of Social Capital and Active Citizenship” – Australian Journal on Volunteering.

¹Luciana Aparecida Gomes is an impeccable professional whose career has evolved across various areas of the pharmaceutical industry – from customer service, reception and verification of pharmaceutical products, sales, logistics, storage, inventory control, and quality verification of inputs, pharmaceutical assistance, humanized treatment, good dispensing practices, and pharmacy care, ensuring drug interchangeability, drafting legal documents for public tenders as per legislation, vendor registration, quotas and purchases, and preparing and monitoring reports for sanitary surveillance. Ms. Luciana Aparecida Gomes’ extraordinary knowledge in the field of pharmaceutical sciences, along with a strong commitment and willingness to help others, has resulted in significant professional achievements and immense contributions made to the broader social community, making Ms. Luciana Aparecida Gomes a highly esteemed and recognized individual in the local community. After obtaining a

Bachelor's degree in Pharmaceutical Sciences, Ms. Luciana Aparecida Gomes entered the workforce and has since never stopped improving her knowledge and skills in various directions, developing a broad set of professional skills over a career spanning nearly two decades. Ms. Luciana Aparecida Gomes began her career in the form of internships while still in school, demonstrating great effort and dedication in managing many complex responsibilities and evolving professionally. Her effort, commitment, versatile experience, and exceptional performances were acknowledged and recognized, propelling Ms. Luciana Aparecida Gomes' career towards more and higher-responsibility roles, from Pharmaceutical Distribution Apprentice and Management Assistant to Pharmaceutical Distribution Operations Manager, Pharmacy Manager, and Corporate Client Service Representative.

[← Post anterior](#)

[Post seguinte →](#)

RevistaFT

A RevistaFT têm 28 anos. É uma **Revista Científica Eletrônica Multidisciplinar Indexada de Alto Impacto e Qualis “B2”**.

Periodicidade mensal e de acesso livre. Leia gratuitamente todos os artigos e publique o seu também [clikando aqui](#).

Contato

Queremos te ouvir.

WhatsApp RJ:

(21) 98159-7352

WhatsApp SP:

(11) 98597-3405

e-Mail:

contato@revistaf
t.com.br

ISSN: 1678-0817

CNPJ:

48.728.404/0001-
22

Conselho Editorial

Editores

Fundadores:

Dr. Oston de
Lacerda Mendes.
Dr. João Marcelo
Gigliotti.

Editor

Científico:

Dr. Oston de
Lacerda Mendes

Orientadoras:

Dra. Hevellyn

CAPES –
Coordenação de
Aperfeiçoament
o de Pessoal de
Nível Superior
(CAPES),
fundação do
Ministério da
Educação (MEC),
desempenha
papel
fundamental na
expansão e
consolidação da
pós-graduação
stricto sensu
(mestrado e
doutorado) em
todos os estados
da Federação.

Andrade
Monteiro
Dra. Chimene
Kuhn Nobre

Revisores:

Lista atualizada
periodicamente
em
revistaft.com.br/expresspediente Venha
fazer parte de
nosso time de
revisores
também!

Copyright © Editora Oston Ltda. 1996
- 2024

Rua José Linhares, 134 - Leblon | Rio
de Janeiro-RJ | Brasil